

THE IMPACT OF CONSUMPTION OF MORINGA PUDDING ON THE VOLUME AND FREQUENCY OF BREASTFEEDING IN PUBTERMOTHERS

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Abstract

Breast milk is the best food for newborn babies and is very important to support the baby's health and development. However, the problem of insufficient breast milk production is still often faced by breastfeeding mothers, especially postpartum mothers. Moringa leaves (*Moringa oleifera*) have long been known to have various health benefits, one of which is increasing breast milk production. This study aims to analyze the impact of consuming Moringa pudding on the volume and frequency of breastfeeding in postpartum mothers. This research uses a mixed method research method with an experimental approach. The data collection technique in this research is observation and literature study. The collected data was then analyzed to determine the relationship between consumption of Moringa pudding with breast milk volume and frequency of breastfeeding in postpartum mothers. The results of the study showed that postpartum mothers who consumed Moringa pudding experienced a significant increase in the volume and frequency of breast milk compared to those before consuming Moringa pudding. This statement is supported by the statistical results of the MANOVA test showing a significance value of 0.001, which shows that there is a significant positive relationship between consumption of Moringa pudding and breast milk volume and breastfeeding frequency. Therefore, Moringa pudding can be a safe and natural alternative to help postpartum mothers increase breast milk production and meet the baby's nutritional needs.

Keywords: Consumption, Moringa Pudding, Volume, Breastfeeding Frequency, Postpartum Mothers.

INTRODUCTION

UNICEF and the world's Ministries of Health recommend that newborn babies receive exclusive breast milk for the first six months of their lives. Exclusive breastfeeding means that babies are only given breast milk without additional food or drink, including water, unless necessary for certain medical indications. This recommendation is given because breast milk contains essential nutrients and antibodies that protect babies from infections and support their optimal growth and development (Sarumi & Sari, 2022). Breast milk contains antibodies which are very useful for babies. These antibodies are also called immunoglobulins, which function to protect babies from various diseases and infections. Breast milk not only provides direct protection against diseases that the baby may encounter, but also helps strengthen the baby's overall immune system. The antibody content in breast milk can adapt to the mother's health conditions and the environment, thereby providing protection that suits the baby's needs (Victoria et al., 2016).

The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) reports that in 2023, the percentage of babies aged less than six months who receive exclusive breast milk nationally will reach 76.70%. This figure increased 0.68% compared to the previous year, which was recorded at 75.87%. Overall, there were 3 provinces that had a percentage of exclusive breastfeeding above the national average last year. North Kalimantan will be the province with the highest percentage of exclusive breastfeeding nationally in

2023, reaching 81.00%. Meanwhile, the lowest level of exclusive breastfeeding nationally was in South Kalimantan last year. The percentage is only 60.27.11%, while in East Kalimantan the percentage is 75.87% (Annur, 2024).

The low practice of exclusive breastfeeding can be caused by various complex factors. One of them is the lack of adequate information and education regarding the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding for baby's health. When the practice of exclusive breastfeeding is low, mothers often switch to using formula milk (formula) as an alternative (Sarumi & Sari, 2022). In the book *Al-Qanun Fii Al-Tibb*, it is stated that one of the causes of insufficient breast milk production is low nutritional intake by breastfeeding mothers. Nutritional deficiencies can affect the quality and quantity of breast milk produced by mothers, so it is important for breastfeeding mothers to pay attention to their diet to support optimal breast milk production. Therefore, various approaches are needed to increase breast milk production, one of which is through improving the nutritional intake of breastfeeding mothers (Prayekti, 2021).

Moringa leaves have long been known to have the potential to increase breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers. Moringa leaves are rich in nutrients such as iron, calcium, vitamin A, vitamin C, and other substances that are important in helping meet the mother's nutritional needs and supporting the lactation process. Apart from that, the vegetable protein contained in Moringa leaves also plays a role in maintaining the health of nursing mothers' bodies, so that they can produce enough breast milk for babies (East Kalimantan Health Office, 2023). The use of Moringa leaves can be implemented in various preparations, one of which is Moringa leaf pudding.

Previous research by Hariyati et al (2023) shows that there is an effect that consumption of Moringa pudding significantly increases the volume and frequency of breastfeeding in mothers who consume it regularly. This can be explained by the nutritional content in Moringa which supports breast milk production, such as being rich in iron, calcium, vitamins A and B complex which are important for the health of mother and baby. Health workers provide health promotion regarding nutrition for postpartum mothers which can increase breast milk production. Similar research by (Carolin et al., 2022) found that Moringa leaf extract capsules have been proven to have a positive influence on breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers. The rich nutritional content in Moringa leaf extract, such as iron, calcium, vitamin A and B complex, can increase the quality and quantity of breast milk produced. Regular consumption can help increase breast milk production levels and provide additional nutrients that are important for the health of mother and baby during the breastfeeding period.

The research results can provide a scientific basis for health workers, such as midwives and doctors, to recommend consuming Moringa pudding to postpartum mothers who experience challenges in breast milk production. This may help increase awareness and acceptance of the use of natural food additives to support lactation. This study aims to analyze the impact of consuming Moringa pudding on the volume and frequency of breastfeeding in postpartum mothers.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a mixed method research method with an experimental approach. Mixed method research is an approach that combines qualitative and quantitative research methods in one study to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the

research problem. This approach allows researchers to explore data in depth (qualitative) while measuring and analyzing data statistically (quantitative) (Dawadi et al., 2021). The data collection technique in this research is observation and literature study. The population of this study was postpartum mothers in the Loa Bakung health center working area. The sampling technique for this research was chosen using a purposive sampling technique with the following criteria:

1. Postpartum mothers who are willing to breastfeed their babies exclusively
2. Postpartum mothers who do not have allergies to Moringa leaves
3. Postpartum mothers who consume Moringa pudding for 7 days

The data that has been collected is then analyzed to determine the relationship between consumption of Moringa pudding with breast milk volume and breastfeeding frequency. Based on this description, this research has a hypothesis:

H1: Consumption of Moringa pudding affects breastfeeding volume in postpartum mothers

H2: Consumption of Moringa pudding affects the frequency of breastfeeding in postpartum mothers

RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

The results of observations carried out in the Loa Bakung Community Health Center area on Jalan Jakarta block AI, Loa Bakung Village, Sungai Kunjang District, Samarinda City, show that in this area there are still significant problems related to the lack of breast milk production in postpartum mothers. Researchers found that many postpartum mothers in the region have difficulty producing sufficient breast milk volume for their babies' needs, which can have a negative impact on the baby's health and development. Factors that may contribute to this problem include lack of proper nutritional intake, post-partum stress, and lack of education about proper breastfeeding techniques.

Considering the importance of breast milk production, researchers collaborated with the Loa Bakung Community Health Center to conduct research on making Moringa leaf pudding as an effort to increase breast milk production. This collaboration aims to explore the potential of Moringa leaves, which are rich in nutrients, in helping postpartum mothers increase the volume and frequency of breastfeeding.

The results obtained based on this research were that there was an increase in breast milk volume after giving Moringa pudding with initial results before giving Moringa pudding, it was found that the average breast milk volume was 78.30 ml with a minimum of 45 ml and 100 ml. The results after giving Moringa pudding showed that the average volume of breast milk was 96.51 ml with a minimum of 58 ml and a maximum of 141 ml.

The results of giving Moringa pudding have shown a significant increase in the frequency of breastfeeding, from poor to good levels. Consuming Moringa pudding has been proven to increase breast milk production, so that breastfeeding mothers tend to breastfeed more often.

Validity test

Validity testing is a method in research that aims to ensure that the instruments or measurement tools used actually measure what should be measured in accordance with the research objectives. The validity test results obtained with a significance value (p-value) below 0.005 indicate that there is strong evidence to support the validity of the measurement.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing aims to evaluate how consistent and reliable a measurement instrument or test tool is in measuring something. Reliability test results with a value above 0.060 indicate that the measurement tool or instrument used can be considered reliable or trustworthy.

Normality test

The normality test is used to test whether the data we have comes from a normal distribution or not. The results of the data normality test show that the data distribution is normally distributed.

Uji MANOVA

The MANOVA (Multivariate Analysis of Variance) test is a statistical method used to test the effect of independent variables on a set of dependent variables together. The MANOVA test results show a significance value of 0.001, which indicates that Moringa pudding has a significant impact on the volume and frequency of breastfeeding.

DISCUSSION

Baby food that meets the best quality and quantity is breast milk (ASI). Breast milk contains all the nutrients a baby needs for optimal growth and development, including protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals in the right proportions. Apart from that, breast milk also contains antibodies and other bioactive substances that help protect babies from infection and disease. Breast milk is easily digested by the baby's digestive system which is still developing and naturally adapts to the baby's nutritional needs as they grow (Widiastuti & Jati, 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of a baby's life and continuing breastfeeding until two years of age or beyond, with appropriate complementary foods introduced after six months. Therefore, breast milk is the best food for babies, fulfilling both the quality and quantity of nutrients needed for optimal health and development (Mundari et al., 2023).

One of the problems that often occurs in postpartum mothers is a lack of breast milk production, which can cause difficulties in meeting the baby's nutritional needs. Lack of breast milk production in postpartum mothers is often a problem experienced by many women after giving birth. Factors that can influence breast milk production include the mother's health condition, such as hormonal disorders or anemia, as well as psychological factors such as stress and anxiety. Apart from that, inappropriate breastfeeding techniques or infrequent breastfeeding can also have a negative impact on breast milk production. Maternal nutrition also plays an important role; An unbalanced diet or nutritional deficiencies can inhibit breast milk production. To overcome this problem, it is important for postpartum mothers to breastfeed more often, improve breastfeeding techniques, manage stress well, and pay attention to

adequate nutritional intake. Guidance from a lactation expert or health professional is also highly recommended to help mothers understand and overcome the breast milk production problems they experience (Niar et al., 2021).

For postpartum mothers in the community Loa Bakung still has many deficiencies in producing breast milk. Considering the importance of breast milk for babies, efforts to increase breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers are very crucial. Breast milk not only provides essential nutrients for the baby's growth and development, but also contains antibodies that help protect the baby from disease. So the lack of breast milk production shows the importance of efforts to increase breast milk production in breastfeeding mothers. Consuming herbal foods or drinks such as Moringa pudding, which contains Moringa oleifera leaves, can be effective in increasing breast milk volume. This emphasizes the need for continued efforts to provide appropriate support and resources to breastfeeding mothers, including understanding the nutritional value of natural foods such as moringa leaves to support optimal quality and quantity of breast milk for the health of the baby and mother.

Moringa leaves are a plant that is widely known for its health benefits. Moringa leaves are rich in nutrients such as vitamins A, C, and E, as well as important minerals such as calcium, iron, and potassium (Sulasmi et al., 2023). Apart from that, Moringa leaves also contain large amounts of antioxidants and anti-inflammatory compounds which are beneficial for body health. The benefits of Moringa leaves include improving the immune system, supporting heart health, and helping regulate blood sugar levels (Marhaeni, 2021). Moringa leaves have also been used traditionally to help increase breast milk production in nursing mothers and can be a good nutritional addition to the daily diet.

Moringa leaves also contain compounds that can stimulate breast milk production, making them a popular choice as a natural galactagogue. Postpartum mothers can consume Moringa leaves in various forms, such as tea, supplement capsules, or foods such as pudding and soup. Regular consumption of Moringa leaves is believed to help increase breast milk volume, provide better nutrition for babies, and support maternal health during the breastfeeding period (Hariyati et al., 2023).

Considering the lack of breast milk production in postpartum mothers in the Loa Bakung Community Health Center area, consuming Moringa leaves can be a useful measure in stimulating breast milk production in postpartum mothers. Moringa leaves are rich in nutrients and bioactive compounds that can support overall body health and function, including breast milk production (Susanti & Nurman, 2022). The nutritional content such as vitamin A, iron and calcium in Moringa leaves can help meet the nutritional needs of breastfeeding mothers, which is an important factor in producing sufficient and quality breast milk. The phytochemical content in Moringa leaves can also help regulate hormones and increase blood flow to the breasts, which is an important factor in breast milk production. Thus, integrating Moringa leaves into the diet of postpartum mothers can help improve the quality and quantity of breast milk produced, apart from other efforts such as proper breastfeeding techniques and adequate emotional support.

The Moringa leaf plant (*Moringa oleifera*) as a herbal plant can be consumed in various forms, including pudding, tea, supplement capsules, and other foods. Moringa leaf pudding is a creative way to consume this nutrient-rich herbal plant. Made by mixing Moringa leaf powder into pudding mixture, Moringa leaf pudding not only provides the

nutritional benefits such as vitamins, minerals and antioxidants from Moringa leaves, but also offers a delicious taste and pleasant texture. For postpartum mothers, Moringa leaf pudding can be a refreshing and easy-to-like alternative to help increase breast milk production. Regular consumption of Moringa leaf pudding is believed to provide additional support in meeting the nutritional needs of mothers and babies during the breastfeeding period (Prayekti et al., 2021).

Thus, consumption of Moringa pudding can have a positive impact on the volume and frequency of breastfeeding in postpartum mothers because of its rich nutritional content. Using Moringa leaves in foods such as pudding can be a comfortable and enjoyable way for postpartum mothers to increase their intake of important nutrients that can affect the quality and quantity of breast milk produced. Although no research specifically confirms its impact, the traditional use of Moringa leaves in daily food is believed to help maintain maternal health and support the breastfeeding process.

Impact of Moringa Pudding Consumption on Breastfeeding Volume in Postpartum Mothers

The results of the study showed that Moringa pudding had an impact on the volume of breastfeeding among postpartum mothers in the Loa Bakung Community Health Center area. The results of this study are supported by Grasiana et al., (2023) who showed that Moringa pudding can increase breast milk production in postpartum mothers, which contributes to increasing breastfeeding volume. Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) is known as a galactagogue, a substance that can stimulate breast milk production because of its rich nutritional content, including vitamins, minerals and antioxidants.

Several previous studies, such as those conducted by Nurachma et al., (2024), stated that pudding made from the Moringa leaf plant (*Moringa oleifera*) can increase breast milk production in postpartum mothers. This is caused by the natural galactagogue properties of Moringa leaves, which help facilitate milk production. In addition, the pudding form makes it easier to consume Moringa leaves regularly and can be a delicious and beneficial alternative for postpartum mothers who are trying to increase lactation. Thus, Moringa leaf pudding can be a practical and natural solution to support successful breastfeeding and provide optimal nutrition for babies.

Thus, consumption of *Moringa oleifera* pudding can help increase the volume of breastfeeding among postpartum mothers in the Loa Bakung Community Health Center area. Moringa leaves, which are rich in important nutrients such as vitamins, minerals and essential amino acids, have natural galactagogue properties that help stimulate breast milk production. So postpartum mothers who regularly consume Moringa pudding experience a significant increase in breast milk production to help meet their babies' nutritional needs more effectively. With an easy-to-consume form and delicious taste, Moringa pudding is a practical and natural solution to support lactation and maternal health during breastfeeding.

Impact of Moringa Pudding Consumption on Breastfeeding Frequency in Postpartum Mothers

Based on the research results, it was found that Moringa pudding has an impact on the frequency of breastfeeding among postpartum mothers in the Loa Bakung Community Health Center area. Providing Moringa pudding has been proven to produce a significant increase in the frequency of breastfeeding from poor to good

levels. By consuming Moringa pudding, breast milk production in nursing mothers increases, which directly influences the mother's tendency to breastfeed more often. This suggests that complementary foods such as moringa pudding can play an important role in supporting the health and nutritional adequacy of breastfeeding mothers and promoting optimal breastfeeding patterns for their babies. These results are related to research by Hasibuan et al., (2020) which stated that before being given Moringa leaves, the average breast milk production in postpartum mothers was 24.55 ml. After intervention with Moringa leaves, the average breast milk production increased significantly to 41.45 ml. This shows that consumption of Moringa leaves can effectively increase breast milk production in postpartum mothers, almost doubling the initial production.

By increasing the volume of breast milk, postpartum mothers can more easily meet their babies' nutritional needs by breastfeeding more often and regularly. Good breastfeeding frequency not only supports the baby's optimal health and growth, but also helps maintain smooth and sustainable breast milk production. Therefore, consuming Moringa leaf pudding can be an effective natural strategy in supporting exclusive breastfeeding practices and the well-being of mothers and babies during the breastfeeding period.

Apart from increasing breast milk production, good breastfeeding frequency is also believed to have the potential to increase overall breast milk production capacity. Frequent and regular breastfeeding practices can stimulate the mammary glands to produce more breast milk and maintain a smooth milk flow. In other words, the more frequently a mother breastfeeds, the more signals it sends to the body to produce breast milk, which in turn helps maintain adequate breast milk volume for the baby. Good breastfeeding frequency also supports the emotional bond between mother and baby, and provides important nutrition for the baby's growth and development. Therefore, the combination of increasing breast milk production and optimal breastfeeding frequency can provide significant health benefits for mothers and babies during the breastfeeding period (Yulianto et al., 2022).

Thus, the impact of consuming Moringa pudding on the frequency of breastfeeding among postpartum mothers in the Loa Bakung Community Health Center area shows the potential to increase breastfeeding activity positively. Moringa pudding, which contains important nutrients such as vitamins, minerals and active compounds from Moringa leaves, can stimulate breast milk production and make it easier for postpartum mothers to provide the necessary nutrition for their babies. Regular consumption of Moringa pudding not only provides various nutritional benefits, but can also increase the mother's comfort and satisfaction in breastfeeding, thus supporting the practice of exclusive breastfeeding recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) for newborn babies.

CONCLUSION

Based on this research, it was found that giving Moringa pudding significantly increased the volume of breast milk in breastfeeding mothers. Before consuming Moringa pudding, the average volume of breast milk was 78.30 ml with a range between 45 ml and 100 ml. After giving Moringa pudding, the average volume of breast milk increased to 96.51 ml with a range between 58 ml and 141 ml. Apart from that, the research results also show that Moringa pudding increases the frequency of

breastfeeding from poor to good levels, because its consumption has been proven to increase breast milk production. This suggests that complementary foods such as moringa pudding can be an effective solution in improving the quality and adequacy of breast milk and supporting more frequent and optimal breastfeeding practices for breastfeeding mothers and their babies. This finding is supported by statistical analysis which shows a significant positive relationship between consumption of Moringa pudding and breast milk volume and breastfeeding frequency. Moringa pudding can be considered a safe and natural alternative to help postpartum mothers increase breast milk production and meet their babies' nutritional needs. Further studies on the long-term impact of Moringa pudding consumption on the volume and frequency of breastfeeding in postpartum mothers, taking into account factors such as:

1. Effect of duration of consumption of Moringa pudding on breast milk production.
2. Comparison of the effectiveness of Moringa pudding with other methods in increasing breast milk production.
3. The effect of additional nutrients in Moringa pudding on breast milk quality.
4. Social and cultural factors that influence the acceptance and compliance of postpartum mothers in consuming Moringa pudding.

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